

Review

Fundamental features of mesoporous functional materials influencing the efficiency of removal of VOCs from aqueous systems: A review

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Mesoporous materials that can remove VOCs from water systems were carefully overviewed.
- Mesoporous functional materials exhibit high sorption capacities for VOCs aq.
- Materials synthesized from fly ashes show very good sorption parameters.
- Surface modification improved VOC sorption in most studied cases.
- Many materials (MS, MOF, ZIF, composites) may play an important role in VOC removal in the future.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are harmful contaminants that are emitted into the environment as a result of various commercial, industrial, and domestic practices. Their presence in water leads to pollution and poses a huge threat to the ecological environment and human health. They are typically released into the environment through a spill or inappropriate disposal which allows the chemicals to get absorbed into the ground or enter the sewage system. Thus far, several treatment methods have been developed to remove VOCs from water, including steam stripping or air stripping, ion exchange, filtration, adsorption, and application of various types of sorbents. Due to their cost-effectiveness and efficiency, the use of mesoporous materials, especially those synthesized from coal fly ash (FA), is recognized as the most promising strategy for slowing down the impact of VOCs. This study is believed to be the first to assess the advances made in improving the adsorption of VOCs by different functional mesoporous materials (FA, zeolites, mesoporous silica, metal organic frameworks). The impact associated with the properties of these materials is carefully summarized in this paper, in regard to their solid-state characteristics, material synthesis method, and surface modification. In addition, their chemical and physical interactions in solution, the reaction kinetics, and the influence of temperature and pH are described in detail. The aim of this work was to compare the sorption properties of the materials synthesized from FA with more complex

Abbreviations: BTEX, benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, xylene; BTX, benzene, toluene, xylene; CCPs, coal combustion products; DDTMA, dodecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide; DHDDMA, dihexadecyl dimethyl ammonium bromide; DMF, *N,N*-dimethylformamide; DODDMA, dioctadecyl dimethyl ammonium bromide; DTDDMA, ditetradecyl dimethyl ammonium bromide; ECEC, external cation exchange capacity; ECOBA, European Coal Combustion Products Association; EO, ethylene oxide; EtOH, ethanol (C₂H₅OH); FAs, fly ashes; FTIR, Fourier-transform infrared; GC-MS, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry; HDTMA-Br, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (C₁₆H₃₃(CH₃)₃NBr); HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography; IR, infrared; MAG, magnetite (γ-Fe₃O₄); MeOH, methanol (CH₃OH); MOFs, metal organic frameworks; MSMs, mesoporous silica materials; NAPh, naphthalene (C₁₀H₈); OTS, octadecyltrichlorosilane; P123, symmetric triblock copolymer (PEO-PPO-PEO); PAHs, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons; PAO, polyalkylene oxide; PDCA, Plan-Do-Check-Act; PEO, polyethylene oxide; PMs, particulate matters; PNP, p-nitrophenol (C₆H₅NO₃); PNT, p-nitrotoluene (C₇H₇NO₂); PPO, polypropylene oxide; PTES, phenyltriethoxysilane (C₁₂H₂₀O₃Si); RGO, reduced graphene oxide; S_w, water solubility; SEM, scanning electron microscopy; SSA, specific surface area (m²/g); TCE, trichloroethylene (C₂HCl₃); TEM, transmission electron microscopy; TGA, thermogravimetric analysis; TOES, tetraethyl orthosilicate (C₈H₂₀O₄Si); VOCs, volatile organic compounds; XPS, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; XRD, X-ray diffraction; XRF, X-ray fluorescence; ZIFs, zeolitic imidazole frameworks.

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FA
Composite

mesoporous materials. This overview provides a comprehensive understanding of VOC removal from water systems using various functional materials, as well as helps in identifying the materials that may play a key role in the future.

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1. Introduction

VOCs are a large class of low-molecular-weight, carbon-containing compounds characterized by high volatility, low vapor pressure (≥ 0.01 kPa at 20 °C), and low water solubility (Herrmann, 2010). Numerous VOCs have been identified, which include toxic substances, such as chloroform, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, benzene, toluene, xylene, and styrene, and carcinogenic compounds (Zhengjian et al., 2014). The risk of exposure to VOCs is determined based on the individual constituents of the compounds, with each having the potential to trigger different symptoms, health effects, and illnesses in humans (Shuai et al., 2018). VOCs are easily absorbed by the skin and mucous membranes and pose damaging effects on human organs and metabolic systems (Huang et al., 2016). Therefore, effective VOC elimination techniques for environmental remediation are of particular importance and in urgent need.

Natural environmental processes as well as human and industrial practices cause the dispersal of a significant amount of VOCs into water. The major categories of organic contaminants present in the water systems are VOCs and synthetic organic chemicals (Fig. 1). VOCs are found in a variety of commercial, industrial, and residential products, including gasoline, solvents, cleaners and degreasers, paints, inks and dyes, and pesticides (Zou et al., 2019). The presence of these compounds in the environment is typically the result of human activities, such as a spill or inappropriate disposal which allows the chemicals to soak into the ground or enter the sewage system. Once released into the environment, VOCs may be carried deeper into an aquifer and evaporate at low concentrations as they move through the subsurface. Most of these compounds can be detected by odor. However, the only way to identify their type and estimate their actual concentration is to perform sampling and testing.

Understanding the sources of VOCs in wastewater and the concentrations at which they are present is necessary. Benzene, methylene chloride,

trichloroethylene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene, and tetrachloroethene are contributed mostly by industries. A study based on sewage monitoring indicated that the concentrations of these compounds ranged from 0 to 46 ppm, and toluene emission was found to be the greatest (Quigley and Corsi, 1995). Commercial sewers usually carry a total VOC concentration of not more than 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$; however, an average amount of 10–21 $\mu\text{g/L}$ has also been reported (Roghani et al., 2018). This number changes in the case of a wastewater treatment plant, where pollutants become concentrated. The concentration of VOCs at the inlet and outlet of an equalization tank was reported as 8796 and 6992 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively, while the total calculated concentration of VOCs (by mass balance approach) was 7303 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Padalkar and Kumar, 2018).

Fig. 1. Contamination of water resources, particularly organic compounds (Muir et al., 2017).

Several treatment methods have been developed for the removal of VOCs from sewage and industrial wastewaters. Currently, VOCs are mostly removed from contaminated wastewater streams by steam stripping or air stripping carried out in combination with carbon adsorption off-gas treatment (Abdullahi et al., 2014). However, many methods have been described in the literature, including ion exchange, filtration, adsorption, and application of various types of highly effective sorbents (Kibazohi et al., 2004; Aivalioti et al., 2012; Almeida et al., 2012; Vidal et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2019a). Due to increasing restrictions on emissions, industries are in need of alternative low-cost, easily available wastewater treatment technologies. Adsorption capacities of low-cost sorbents for application in wastewater treatment are of particular interest (Gisi et al., 2016; Crini et al., 2019). The affinity of mineral sorbents toward organic pollutants, their applications, costs, and consideration of their reuse after the adsorption processes have been discussed (Bandura et al., 2017; Muir et al., 2017). Going forward, FAs and their transformation products have been recognized as excellent sorbents of organic compounds due to properties such as high specific surface area, stability, ion exchange, and unusual pore distribution. Moreover, their synthesis is relatively cheap and commercially performed. FAs and their products belong to a popular group of components that are currently discussed in the literature as mesoporous functionalized materials with designed sorption properties. These include synthetic zeolites, MOFs, mesoporous silica nanocomposites, SBA-15, MCM-41, MCM-48, and KIT-6 (Serrano et al., 2004; Dou et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020).

The presence of a neutral or negatively charged surface results in the low or no affinity of mesoporous materials toward polar organic compounds. The possibility of their functionalization by changing the surface charge and their application as sorbents of organic compounds have been analyzed in several studies (Li and Bowman, 1998; Bowman, 2003; Bandura et al., 2015; Szala et al., 2015). Surface functionalization can be carried out in three ways: subsequent surface functionalization of silica materials (grafting); simultaneous condensation of corresponding silica and organosilica precursor groups; and incorporation of organic groups as bridging components into the pore walls (mesoporous organosilica) (Hoffmann et al., 2006). Replacing the exchangeable positively charged cations with different ions might neutralize the negative charge on the surface of materials. Very often, the introduction of a surfactant alters the chemistry of the surface, allowing synthetic minerals to adsorb nonpolar organic solutes (Franus et al., 2014). The use of mesoporous functional materials as efficient sorbents has been investigated as an alternative strategy to the existing high-cost methods of VOC removal from water solutions. These materials can be modified by inorganic salts, organic surfactants, metals, or metal oxides to increase their adsorption capacity (Muir et al., 2017). The unique ion exchange and adsorption properties make them suitable for application in the removal of organic compounds such as VOCs, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, and other complex petrochemicals. More importantly, many mesoporous materials can be synthesized from FAs, which are mostly waste products resulting from coal transformation.

Throughout the world, coal accounts for approximately 38% of power generation. Coal ash, a waste product obtained from coal combustion, consists of FAs, bottom ash, boiler slag, and flue gas desulfurization material (Zierold and Odoh, 2020). FAs, which are the main components of coal ash, are composed of spherical particulate matter characterized by a diameter of 0.1 μm to greater than 100 μm and wide applications due to its distinct properties. FAs are dust-like, fine-particle inorganic materials that mainly contain metal oxides such as Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , CaO , MgO , and Na_2O (Blissett and Rowson, 2012), an amorphous phase represented by a glassy phase, unburned carbon residues (Ahmaruzzaman, 2010), numerous trace elements (Li, Be, Sr, Hf, Y, Zr, Nb, Mo, Cs, Ba, La, Ce, Nd, Sm, Eu, Tb, Dy, Yb, Lu, Ta), and radionuclides (Th, U) (Vassilev and Vassileva, 1997).

FAs have been recognized as cost-effective sorbents of harmful water contaminants, including VOCs (Kwong and Chao, 2010; Ge et al., 2018). Recent research has proved that these materials could also be extensively used as raw materials for synthesizing mesoporous materials including MOFs, geopolymers, synthetic zeolites, and mesoporous silica (Chandrasekar and Ahn, 2008; Basu et al., 2009; Majchrzak-Kucęba and Nowak, 2011; Blissett and Rowson, 2012; Franus et al., 2014; Ge et al., 2018; Ściubidło and Majchrzak-Kucęba, 2019; Zhu et al., 2019a). To ensure a sustainable future for the environment and the local ecosystem, it is particularly important to reuse and recycle industrial wastes. Therefore, the use of FAs is in line with the concept of circular economy and zero waste.

Due to their increasing occurrence in water resources and harmful effects on human health and the environment, considerable attention is still devoted to analyzing the removal of VOCs from aqueous solutions. As discussed, functionalized mesoporous materials are acknowledged as future sorbents for eliminating organic compounds. Moreover, the use of these materials is advantageous as they can be applied not only to the aqueous phase but also to the soil and gas phase. This study aimed to reveal the efficiency of VOC removal from water systems with the use of mesoporous functional materials. For this purpose, a number of materials were compared, and their properties and suitability were evaluated. An important goal of this work was to show whether the use of FAs for the synthesis of mesoporous materials is the right direction and results in a product that stands out in terms of parameters as well as sorption efficiency. Many previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of FAs in reducing the concentrations of VOCs in water, the results of which are summarized in this paper, along with a detailed analysis of the gaps that should be fulfilled.

This review discusses the behaviors exhibited by VOCs during neutralization using mesoporous functional materials, together with the sorption efficiency which is determined by various factors (sorbent characteristics, concentration of solutions, type of compounds, coexistence of other impurities). As a large number of studies have analyzed the sorption of volatile compounds, this review focuses only on the clean-up of water pollution. Particular attention has been paid to the mesoporous materials synthesized from FAs, considering the scarcity of natural resources and pure raw materials, as well as environmental protection and the possibility of using residual waste.

The novelty of this research was to compare and highlight the importance of using alternative sorbents synthesized from waste materials such as fly ash. Water systems' contamination with VOCs is a significant environmental pollution issue and in this paper's authors compared over 20 different materials and indicated those with the greatest application potential. Moreover, comprehensive research on the application of organically modified mesoporous functional materials was performed. The authors also include an economic and environmental analysis where discussing the possibility of commercialization, which was not done in review articles concerning VOCs' removal from water systems before.

1.1. Economic analysis

Systematic research efforts on synthesis and adsorption properties of mesoporous materials were initiated in the late 1930's and the first concern of zeolites (Yilmaz and Müller, 2009). Since that time, the commercial impact of the introduction of synthetic mesoporous materials into refinery operations has been immense. Based on this successful entry into the industrial scene, synthetic zeolites quickly found many applications in petroleum processing in subsequent years (Yilmaz and Müller, 2009). Nowadays, the synthetic zeolites market was valued at USD 13.67 Billion in 2017. Consumption for adsorbent/desiccant applications accounts for the smallest share (14% of world consumption of synthetic zeolites in 2016), but will be the fastest-growing market, driven by the recovery of construction markets, the natural gas market, and environmental applications especially trapping VOCs to prevent

release into the environment. Given the growing demand for this type of synthetic materials, scientists all over the world have started to work intensively on the synthesis of mesoporous materials that can be used as sorbents for organic compounds.

The most popular mesoporous materials, however, are made of pure reagents, which make them not the most ecological material. The materials synthesized from fly ash proposed by many researchers are an alternative to expensive technologies (Veerapandian et al., 2019). Taking into account the trends in the organic sorbents market, the final cost of 1 kg of sorbent should not exceed \$ 1 (Lamplugh et al., 2020). Most commercially available sorbents are designed to remove water-immiscible organic compounds from its surface. As for the use of sorbents to remove dissolved VOC contaminants from wastewater, such applications on an industrial scale are not popular (Crini et al., 2019). On the other hand, there is a great demand on the market for sorption technology for the treatment of industrial wastewater contaminated by VOCs (refinery, paint industry, plastic industry, pharmaceutical industry). Interestingly, research shows that in the case of some volatile substances, the use of synthetic sorption materials should bring better results than competing natural materials such as currently used diatomites or bentonites. Due to the lack of an eco-friendly and economical sorbent of VOCs, still the most popular techniques for their removal from contaminated wastewater are steam stripping or air stripping carried out in combination with carbon adsorption off-gas treatment (Abdullahi et al., 2014). Fly ash-based sorbents can be a breakthrough due to their availability, low cost and environmentalism.

1.2. Environmental analysis

Due to an abrupt industrial development since late 60's in 20th century, and an excessive use of natural resources, including fossil fuels, wastes, by products and tailings are generated in an overwhelming amounts worldwide. Therefore, a need to responsibly manage such wastes and avoid creation of voluminous dumpsites and landfills, is of the greatest importance for both, the integrity of almost all environmental components and human's health. Coal thermal conversion, among other industrial processes, such as steel and cement production, is considered as one of the most exhaustive, anthropogenic activity for the air quality and particulate matters (PMs) emissions (Ge et al., 2018). According to ECOBA, in 2016, almost 40Mt of CCPs were generated in coal thermal power plants across European Union countries, from which 63.8% were fly-ashes (ca. 25,53 Mt/annum). Several approaches were presented to effectively manage and valorize fly-ashes by chemical treatment (e.g. hydrothermal activation) (Wołowiec et al., 2017a; Czuma et al., 2019) and their incorporation into production processes, since relatively high specific surface area, large porosity and presence of various mineral phases, are advantageous from the perspective of their reuse.

Furthermore, the whole array of implementation areas of fly-ashes and their synthetic derivatives, seem to be an unprecedented opportunity to effectively and responsibly recycle industrial tailings and to fully comply with a circular economy model. Fly-ashes and their synthetic counterparts, such as zeolites and MSMs (Muir et al., 2017; Franus et al., 2019) have been recently successfully introduced as secondary raw-materials in civil engineering (Habert et al., 2011; Ramujee 2019), remediation (Terzano et al., 2005), water pollution abatement (Yeheyis et al., 2009; Szala et al., 2015; Muir and Bajda, 2016; Wołowiec et al., 2017a), heterogenous catalysis (Babajide et al., 2012; Mahyuddin et al., 2019) and green chemistry (Li et al., 2017).

In all abovementioned areas of implementation it is worth highlighting the broad spectrum in which fly-ash, as industrial by-product, could be applied and to see an enhanced, hidden, chemical potential because of which this mineral matrix can be converted into more stable materials with tunable porosity, larger specific surface area and greater share of pores with specifically desired dimensions.

To evaluate the proper approach once deciding which material to use in VOCs abatement in water solutions, a Deming Cycle and PDCA analysis would be advantageous (Realyv et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2020). First of all, a need to plan desired properties of the materials after transformation procedure, and detailed description of the areas of their implementation is crucial in the first stage of the PDCA analysis. Afterwards, a chemical or physical transformation procedure of the secondary raw-material (fly-ash) should be performed. Moreover, a functionalization of the fly-ash derivative, by changing its surface charge or introduction of a catalytically active, metal atoms, might be of importance.

Sequel to "Do" step, a verification ("Check") of the transformation procedure to the desired materials (preferably synthetic zeolites and MSMs) should be verified by performing an advanced instrumental analyses: XRD (phase analysis), XRF (chemical composition determination), SEM-EDS, TEM (assessment of the micromorphology and sizes of material's grains), FTIR (presence of the surface, functional groups). After specific VOCs sorption experiments, both GC-MS and HPLC, might be applied to measure quantitatively and qualitatively the amount of adsorbed VOC. Furthermore, after sorption tests, a XPS analysis would be beneficial to verify if any chemical bonds are created between sorbent and sorbate.

Final stage of the PDCA approach, once deciding which materials to choose for VOCs sorption from waters, would be to run sorption experiments and perform a desorption tests in order to verify if fly-ash based sorbents may be effectively regenerated. Furthermore, having an industrial partner to exactly know the real problem of excessive VOCs concentration in sludge or water, seem to be beneficial from the perspective of the commercial technology development. Abovementioned PDCA analysis with detailed description of each stage (Plan, Do, Check and Act) is depicted as Fig. 2.

2. Materials and their sorption properties

In this review, the properties of FAs and advanced mesoporous functional materials have been compiled to determine their potential in the removal of VOCs from aqueous systems. The main focus of the paper is modern mesoporous materials, especially those synthesized from FAs. Around the globe, there are billion tons of waste materials that should be used in the first place before the raw materials. A variety of mesoporous materials have been identified and categorized into the following groups: FAs (substrates for the synthesis of many functional materials), synthetic zeolites, mesoporous silica, MOFs, biochar and nanocomposites. To provide a clear view of the described materials, their characterization and properties are summarized in Table 1. All mesoporous materials with proven effectiveness in the removal of VOCs from water systems are described in the presented overview, but the intention is to compare these materials and assess whether the transformation products of FAs can be considered as future materials for the treatment of polluted waters. Therefore, the removal efficiency of various mesoporous materials is compared with each other and the influence of the materials' features on their removal efficiency is highlighted in Table 2.

Different approaches have been developed to synthesize mesoporous material using: naturally occurring plants, chemical sources like silicon alkoxide and expensive structure directing agents (Chandrasekar and Ahn, 2008; Linares et al., 2014; Ahmad et al., 2014) (Fig. 3). However, in response to the growing environment concern, sustainability issues associated with the silica precursors, harsh synthetic conditions and high cost of its production limit their manufacture is at industrial scale (Gérardin et al., 2013; Assi et al., 2020). In order to increase the recycling of the coal fly ash several transformation technologies were developed (Assi et al., 2020). The large number of methods for obtaining mesoporous materials from FA is based on a similar hydrothermal synthesis technology (Chang et al., 1999; Kazemian et al., 2010; Wdowin et al., 2014;

Fig. 2. PDCA analysis in the valorization of the fly-ash by-product and organic fraction of municipal solid wastes.

Bandura et al., 2015, 2016; Zgureva and Boycheva, 2015; Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020). The differences consisting in varying different parameters such as: pH, the temperature and the time of hydrothermal or aging treatment and also the quantities of raw materials or reagents (H_2O , NaOH). These variations influenced more or less the obtained material properties like crystalline phase, pore size and texture parameters (Ojha et al., 2004) (Fig. 4). It was found that most of the Si and Al components in the FA could be effectively transformed into mesoporous materials, depending on the hydrothermal conditions (Bandura et al., 2015). Preparing advance mesoporous materials with cheap FA is an important way to promote the use of additional value.

2.1. Fly ash

FA is rich in metallic oxides, in the order $SiO_2 > Al_2O_3 > Fe_2O_3 > CaO > MgO > K_2O$ and large amount of unburned carbon. Furthermore, FA contains trace elements that can have a negative impact on the environment (Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020). Usually, the content of metallic oxides in fly ash is depended by the coal type - SiO_2 contents were higher in the fly ash derived from sub-bituminous (40%–60%) and bituminous (20%–60%) samples than in lignite samples (15%–45%) (Koornneef et al., 2006; Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020). The same trend was seen for Al_2O_3 . FA are characterized by varied specific surface area – 5–10 m^2/g and poorly developed pore structure. The degree of development of the grain surface and the size of specific surface area to a large extent determine their usefulness as a sorbents (Cheerarat and Jaturapitakkul, 2004). However, in the case of adsorption processes, where we deal only with the surface phenomenon, fly ash has been used many times.

FAs as a raw industrial by-product were researched as a cost-effective sorbent of harmful environmental components and toxic VOCs in both water solutions and gaseous mixtures. Due to their relatively high porosity and presence of unburned carbon residues with high micropore volume, FAs show high affinity and good adsorption capacity toward certain VOCs (Wang et al., 2008) (Table 2). Banerjee et al. (1997) performed a sorption kinetics study focusing on the removal of one of the xylene isomers - o-xylene onto FAs as a function of temperature, initial concentration of sorbate, and particle size of sorbent. The

authors reported that the rate of sorption of o-xylene by FAs was high during the first 30 min of the sorption process and that effective adsorption can be achieved by the diffusion of solute into the micropores and capillaries of the unburned carbon residues in FAs as these materials act as active sites for adsorbing o-xylene effectively from the aqueous solution. Furthermore, they proved that with a higher initial concentration of o-xylene, the rate of uptake of sorbate was higher. Investigation of the sorption rate as a function of temperature confirmed that with the increase in temperature, the sorption efficiency of o-xylene increases. Sorption of o-xylene was reported as a first-order and reversible reaction.

Sharan et al. (2009), on the other hand, performed a study on phenol sorption from aqueous solutions utilizing FAs collected from a thermal power plant located in Chandrapura, India. The influence of the adsorbent dosage, solution pH, and initial concentration of C_6H_6O was investigated by the authors. Their results showed that the optimum sorbent dosage for effective phenol removal (with efficiency up to 95.7%) was 7 g/dm^3 and that further increase in dosage did not improve the sorption capacity. Adsorption capacity of FAs slightly increased with pH, with the highest capacity noted at pH 8 (98.5% removal of phenol), and decreased with pH values above 8. These variations in adsorption efficiency as a function of pH may be attributed to the electrostatic interactions occurring between the phenolate ions ($C_6H_5O^-$) and the protonated surface of FAs at low pH, which corresponds to higher phenol removal from acidic ($2 > pH > 6$) and slightly basic ($7 > pH > 8$) solutions. Further increase of pH results in poorer phenol adsorption capacity, which is probably due to the competitive interactions occurring between the hydroxyl anions (OH^-) and the above-mentioned phenolate ions ($C_6H_5O^-$). The initial phenol concentration also affects the sorption efficiency, with the highest efficiency achieved at the concentration of 700 mg/dm^3 (Table 2).

However, the utilization of FAs as sorbents involves the potential leaching of some elements into the water, which will lead to secondary environmental pollution (Adegoke et al., 2017). It was found that the particles on the surface layer of FAs contain a significant amount of readily leachable material that gets deposited during cooling after combustion. Therefore, the charge of the particles on the FA surface and the formation of a double-diffusion layer play a significant role in leaching (Adegoke et al., 2017). Hence, regardless of the good sorption properties

Table 1
Detailed comparison of materials used in VOC sorption experiments: origin and modification. S_{BET} , parameters that were mainly focused, and the list of compounds removed from aqueous solutions.

Material	Synthesis method	Modification method	S_{BET} surface area [m ² /g]	Comments/observations/solid-state characterization	Type of VOCs	References
FA FAs (from the bituminous coal)	By-products of coal combustion	No modification. FA was used as the sorbent material in this research. Samples were obtained from the electrical power-generating stations owned and operated by the Public Service Electricity and Gas Co. of New Jersey. These FAs were derived from the bituminous coal obtained from the eastern United States coal mines.	6	The individual particle size of this material ranges between 0.5 and 100 μm. The major components of FA are alumina, silica, iron oxide, calcium oxide, and residual carbon.	o-Xylene	Banerjee et al. (1997)
FA	By-product of coal combustion	Samples were collected from the Chandrapura Thermal Power Plant, Jharkhand, India. They were not subjected to any synthesis or treatment processes.	9.44	Cation-exchange capacity of FA was 30.34 meq/100 g. pH was 6.86. 0.64% of organic carbon was determined.	Phenol	Sharan et al. (2009)
Biochars Neem tree Bamboo tree Sugarcane	Raw materials (neem tree, bamboo, sugarcane) were collected from CSRI-NEERI campus in Nagpur (India). Transformation of biomass feedstocks was carried out utilizing slow pyrolysis process at three different temperature regimes: 350 °C, 450 °C and 550 °C	Raw biochars obtained after slow pyrolysis process at three, different temperatures (350 °C, 450 °C, 550 °C) were subsequently subjected to sorption experiments in respect to six VOC molecules from water solutions. No further modification of materials was implemented.	43.9 (at temperature of pyrolysis equal to 550 °C) – 2.29 (at temperature of pyrolysis equal to 550 °C)	Pyrolysis temperature greatly affects the elementary composition of obtained biochars - the higher the pyrolysis temperature, the greater the C content and lower content of H and N in all examined biomass feedstocks. What is more, the acidity of surface functional groups enhances attraction of hydrophilic VOCs molecules. SSA and porosity of obtained biochars increases while increasing pyrolysis temperature, which may be associated with deterioration of long carbon chains within lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose carbohydrates and phase transition to biochar.	Benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride	Kumar et al. (2019)
Pine needles	Pine needles were collected from lawns present in Kangwon National University campus in Cheoncheon (Gangwon province) South Korea	Dried, crushed and sieved (<1.0 mm particle size) pine needles were pyrolyzed at three different temperatures: 300 °C, 500 °C and 700 °C at a heating rate equal to 7 °C/min. No modification of the obtained biochars was applied.	4.09 (at temperature of pyrolysis equal to 300 °C), 13.06 (at temperature of pyrolysis equal to 500 °C), 390.52 (at temperature of pyrolysis equal to 700 °C)	The same as observed by Kumar et al. (2019) while increasing the pyrolysis temperature, the SSA and porosity of biochars obtained from pine needles increased. Biochars produced at 300 and 500 were dominantly mesoporous whereas biochar obtained at 700 was a microporous material.	TCE	Ahmad et al. (2013)
Orange peel-MAG modified	Orange peel powder slowly pyrolyzed at three different temperatures (250 °C, 400 °C and 700 °C)	Orange peel powder was co-precipitated with MAG (γ-Fe ₃ O ₄) in water solution and subsequently pyrolyzed at 250 °C, 400 °C and 700 °C with the heating rate from 100 °C equals to 5 °C/min.	41.2 (temperature of pyrolysis: 250 °C), 23.4 (temperature of pyrolysis: 400 °C) and 19.4 (temperature of pyrolysis: 700 °C)	FTIR spectra of all biochars revealed vast presence of -OH, -NH ₂ and -CH ₂ functional groups. Introduction of the MAG nanoparticles greatly lowered C content in modified biochars and increased the content of ash. Furthermore, the SSA of MAG-modified biochars decreased compared to non-modified samples (e.g. 19.4 m ² /g and 501 m ² /g, for samples pyrolyzed at 700 °C, respectively)	NAPH and PNT	Chen et al. (2011)
Synthetic zeolites Zeolite Na-Y	Hydrothermal, purchase from Marc and Sigma	OTS-modified [CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₇ SiCl ₃ , 95%], 1.0 g of Na-Y zeolite was added into 50 mL of toluene solution containing 500 mmol OTS. The solution was stirred for 30 min and separated with a 0.45-mm filter. The solid was rinsed with EtOH anhydrous and chloroform (95%), and placed in an oven at 110 °C for 5 h to obtain the powder of OMZ.	470	HY zeolite has a low ratio of Si/Al and less hydrophobic surface. After Na-Y zeolite is modified with OTS, both its surface area and pore volume decrease, but the average pore size increases. OTS coats the zeolite surface in the form of a monolayer. The results demonstrated that OMZ possesses hydrophobic external surface and hydrophilic internal surface—it is an amphiphilic material.	Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, propylbenzene, trichloromethane, n-pentanol, m-cresol, and phenol	Chao et al. (2012)
Zeolite Na-X	Hydrothermal	20 g of F-class FA, 0.5 dm ³ of 3 mol/dm ³ NaOH at 75 °C for 24 h, and HDTMA-Br treatment according to the ECEC values.	282.6 ^a	Crystals of pure Na-X zeolite up to 70% wt., with admixture of mullite (3Al ₂ O ₃ ·2SiO ₂), quartz (SiO ₂), and calcite (α-CaCO ₃) phases. Surface modification reduced V_{tot} to 0.99 and S_{BET} of zeolite Na-X from 282.6 to 48.6 m ² /g. Cp	p-Xylene, toluene, benzene, and ethylbenzene	Franus et al. (2014); Bandura et al. (2015); and Wolowicz

					and Na-X modified by HDTMA in an amount of 1.0 ECEC had an S_{BET} of 17.75 and 48.6 m ² /g, respectively. Surfactants attached to the zeolite Na-X surface may block the porosity. Since the mean pore diameter of zeolite 4A is smaller than nanoparticle size (60–80 nm), nanoparticles cannot be placed in its pores or channels with a pore diameter smaller than 60 nm. It could be assumed that the nanoparticles are located on the surface and the pores of the zeolite 4A with a diameter larger than nanoparticle size. The reduction in the mean pore diameter of the zeolite 4A due to the modification could be related to the sitting of nanoparticles into the pores with a diameter larger than nanoparticle size.			et al. (2017a)
Zeolite 4A	Cu- and Ni-modified	Hydrothermal	Zeolite was mixed with 200 mL of copper nitrate trihydrate salt (0.1 M). Then, 6 g of the prepared zeolite was added to the copper nanoparticle suspension and stirred for 2 h. The above steps were also used for nickel modification (nickel nitrate hexahydrate salt and nickel nanoparticles).	2.77				Mamaghani et al. (2020)
Zeolite Na-P1	Hydrothermal	Zeolite synthesis: 20 kg of F-class FA, 90 dm ³ of 3.3 mol/dm ³ NaOH solution for 36 h at 80 °C. Modification: using DDTMA, didodecyl dimethyl ammonium bromide, tetradecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, DTDDMA, HDTMA, DHDDMA, octadecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, and DODDMA in amounts of 1.0 ECEC.	74.91					Frans (2011); Szala et al. (2015); and Wolowiec et al. (2017b)
Zeolite Na-P1	Hydrothermal	Zeolite Na-P1 was suspended in 200 mL of chitosan solution in glycolic acid and stirred for 32 h. Then, the suspension was adjusted to pH 9 using NaOH and washed with distilled water.	98.5					Bandura et al. (2020)
HZSM-5 nanozeolite	Hydrothermal	Initial calcination of raw CFA at 800 °C for 6 h to remove carbonaceous residues and addition of tetrapropylammonium bromide as an organic structure-directing agent and TEOS as an additional silica source was followed by crystallization at 160 °C for 48 h. The resulting solution was centrifuged and calcined for 6 h at 550 °C. The obtained Na-ZSM-5 material was treated with NH ₄ Cl solution at 90 °C for 5 h and centrifuged again, dried (110 °C for 12 h), and subjected to final calcination at 550 °C for 5 h. The proton form of Na-ZSM-5/180 was prepared by subjecting 2.2. Sorbent characterization the zeolite to a three-fold ion exchange with a 1 M ammonium nitrate solution (5 mL/g), drying for 10 h at 393 K and finally calcined for 0.5 h at 773 K (heating ramps at 10 K/min).	-					Asl et al. (2020)
ZSM-5	Supplied by CU Chemie Uetikon as calcined and template-free material	Multistep synthesis from chemicals	HDTMA-Br was used as a template without calcination ¹ , with CTMA-Br and NaOH dissolved in distilled water, followed by mixing for 24 h and drying at 50 °C. The obtained gel was heated up to 100 °C for 72 h, filtered, washed, and dried. The final step involved calcination of the obtained solid product at 550 °C for 5 h. ² Microwave-irradiation synthesis was performed to develop nanosize crystals.	-398				Meininghaus and Prin (2000)
MCM-41	Multistep synthesis from chemicals			21042				¹ Chiari et al. (2004) and ² Won-jin et al. (2007)
MOFs	MIL-101	Microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis		3900				Jhung et al. (2006)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Material	Synthesis method	Modification method	S_{BET} surface area [m ² /g]	Comments/observations/solid-state characterization	Type of VOCs	References
MOF-AgTz-1	Synthesis from pure chemicals	Further purification was done by a two-step filtration process and extraction with EtOH. Water solution of silver nitrate (AgNO ₃) with 3,5-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazole in the molar ratio of 1:1 was used. Then, the white precipitate was collected, washed several times with pure EtOH, and dried under vacuum conditions for 24 h.	n.d. ^{a,b}	MIL-101. The material was thermally stable up to 275 °C as shown by thermogravimetry/differential thermal analysis. Pure crystalline structure (XRD measurements) of the obtained MOF-AgTz-1 based on the available database.	PNP	Miao et al. (2020)
MOF-199	Synthesis from pure chemicals	Copper (II) nitrate trihydrate (Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·3H ₂ O) was mixed with 1,3,5-tribenzenocarboxylic acid, DMF, EtOH, and double-distilled water. Then, the solution was heated for 48 h up to 85 °C. Afterward, the obtained blue crystals were washed several times with DMF and EtOH. Finally, the blue-violet crystals were dried at 170 °C for 8 h.	2271	N ₂ sorption/desorption curves revealed that the pores of MOF-199 were homogenous and that specific surface area (S_{BET}) exceeded those reported in the previous studies. SEM microimaging showed the octahedral morphology of the crystallites and their size ranging between 20 and 30 μm.	Phenol and PNP	Giraldo et al. (2017)
MIL-68-Al-RGO	One-step solvothermal synthesis	Infinite straight chains of AlH ₂ O ₆ were assembled by interconnection with terephthalate ligands and hydroxyl groups.	761.97 ^c	Uniform distribution of oxygen, aluminum, and carbon was confirmed by SEM-energy-dispersive spectroscopy and TEM microimaging. FTIR analysis revealed bands at 754 cm ⁻¹ (-C-H groups), 1512 and 1701 cm ⁻¹ (-C=O groups), and 1097 cm ⁻¹ indicating the presence of benzene ring from terephthalic acid ligands and a band at 3425 cm ⁻¹ associated with hydroxyl functional groups (-OH).	PNP	Zhibin et al. (2016)

^a Synthesized from FA.^b No data available.^c With 15% wt. load of RGO.

Table 2
Detailed comparison of VOC sorption experiments: process parameters, sorption efficiency, and fundamental features influencing removal efficiency.

Material	Sorption		Fundamental features influencing efficiency		References	
	VOCs	Solvent	Sorption efficiency [mg/g]	Sorbent/solution ratio		
FA	FA from the bituminous coal	20, 100, and 150 mg/L	4	1/30	The results of this research demonstrated that the adsorption reaction can be approximated to first-order reversible kinetics. A significant correlation was observed between the rate of adsorption and the inverse of the square of the particle diameter. The adsorption of o-xylene was an exothermic process and was spontaneous at the temperature investigated. Activation energies for the sorption process ranged between 3.1 and 4.3 kcal/mol. The rate at which o-xylene was adsorbed onto FA was found to be controlled by the diffusion process.	Banerjee et al. (1997)
Biochars	FA from the Chandrapura Thermal Power Plant	100 mg/L	The phenol uptake rates at the initial phenol concentrations of 100, 500, and 1000 mg/L were found to be 13.46, 68.96, and 136.81 mg/g, respectively	From 1/100 to 1/10	The optimum pH was found to be 8. Adsorption equilibrium studies indicated that an optimum contact time of 2 h is required for maximum adsorption of phenol at all the different initial concentrations studied.	Sharan et al. (2009)
	Neem tree	n.d.a. ^a	54.6, 65.5, 39.61, 60.2, 30.81 and 40.99 for benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride respectively ^b	n.d.a. ^a	Neem-based biochars revealed the best sorption capacity in respect to all six VOCs molecules assessed in this study. Sorption process was greatly affected by temperature of slow pyrolysis, as observed by Chen et al. (2011); Ahmad et al. (2013). What is more it was assumed that with higher pyrolysis temperatures, pores become internally connected which favours the free diffusion of VOCs molecules and their retention.	Kumar et al. (2019)
	Bamboo tree		38.61, 44.92, 31.16, 29.7, 25.31, 29.63 for benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride respectively ^b		Higher temperature of neem-tree, bamboo and sugarcane slow pyrolysis favours development of higher SSA and internally linked pores of different dimensions (tubular and honeycomb). Moreover, increased surface acidity, connected with oxygenated functional groups present in samples with greater carbon content, hence pyrolyzed at temperatures above 450 °C is associated with privileged attraction of hydrophilic VOCs molecules.	
	Sugarcane		1.9, 13.8, 9.35, 1.5, 9.62, 9.3 for benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride respectively ^b			
	Pine needles	100 mg/L stock solution of TCE (working solutions ranging from 5 to 50 mg/L)	71,108 89,730 99,733 mg/g for biochars pyrolyzed at 300, 500, 700 °C, respectively	0.3/1000	Removal of TCE from water solutions increased with increasing temperature of slow pyrolysis process, hence greater developed specific surface area of the biochars and higher share of micropores. Ion exchange and chemisorption might be neglected in terms of TCE sorption by pine-needles biochars.	Ahmad et al. (2013)
	Orange peel-MAG modified	18 mg/L for NAPH and 318 mg/L for PNT	Orange peel-magnetite modified biochar pyrolyzed at 250 °C = 13.25 mg of NAPH and 94.13 mg of PNT, Orange peel-magnetite modified biochar pyrolyzed at 400 °C =	6.25/1000	It was observed that the introduction of MAG nanoparticles reduced SSA of obtained biochars and diminish ability to effectively adsorb NAPH and PNT molecules. It would be associated with insufficient active sites available to interact with polar VOCs molecules and permanently remove them from	Chen et al. (2011)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Material	Sorption VOCs	Concentration	Solvent	Sorption efficiency [mg/g]	Sorbent/solution ratio	Fundamental features influencing efficiency	Comments/observations	References
Synthetic zeolites	Zeolite Na-Y	Ranging from 55 to 60,000 mg/L	Water	1.26 mg of NAPH and 22.26 mg of PNT Orange peel-magnetite modified biochar pyrolyzed at 700 °C = 16.65 mg of NAPH and 294.15 mg of PNT	1/50	NAPH and PNT. The unmodified Na-Y weakly adsorbed organic compounds, but exhibited high uptake of those organic compounds that could form hydrogen bonds with the zeolite surface. For the OMZ, however, the organic compounds with low S_w partitioned to the OTS on the modified zeolites to increase their sorption dramatically, while the organic compounds with high S_w adsorbed on the internal pore surfaces to maintain their high adsorption capacities.	aqueous solution.	Chao et al. (2012)
	Zeolite Na-X	10, 50, and 100 ppm	Water + 0.2% MeOH	Na-Y: Benzene = 4 Toluene = 3.7 Ethylbenzene = 1.9 Propylbenzene = 0.35 Phenol = 20 Trichloromethane = 2.5 OTS-modified Na-Y: Ethylbenzene = 23 Toluene = 15 Benzene = 12 Propylbenzene = 3.5 Benzene: Na-X = 3.12 1.0 HDTMA = 3.29 2.0 HDTMA = 3.46 Toluene: Na-X = 4.06 1.0 HDTMA = 4.93 2.0 HDTMA = 5.06 Ethylbenzene: Na-X = 2.83 1.0 HDTMA = 2.59 2.0 HDTMA = 2.63 Paraxylene: Na-X = 1.50 1.0 HDTMA = 6.50 2.0 HDTMA = 6.24	1/50	Parameters such as Si/Al ratio, textural parameters, and EEC had an impact on the sorption efficiency. Surface modification of Na-X zeolites improved their sorption ability for BTEX. The properties of zeolites, in particular the Si/Al ratio, determined their sorption capacity in the case of sorption of BTEX. The higher the Si/Al ratio, the better was the sorption of organic compounds. Hydrophobicity was more important than the textural parameters.		Wolowicz et al. (2017a)
Zeolite 4A	Benzene, toluene, and xylene	10 mg/L	Water	2–9 mg/g The modification only slightly improves the sorption efficiency. The main emphasis in the article, however, is the characteristics of a solid.	1/100	After the gradual filling of adsorbent sites, diffusion of the BTX into the adsorbents was the dominant adsorption mechanism, and the adsorption was slow upon reaching equilibrium. The surface area and available vacant sites increased with increase in the adsorbent content.	The nickel nanoparticle-modified zeolite was a more efficient adsorbent in comparison with others. The addition of copper/nickel nanoparticles increased the surface area of the zeolite adsorbent, which improved adsorption.	Mamaghani et al. (2020)
Zeolite Na-P1	Benzene, ethylbenzene, toluene, p-xylene, and hexane	50 ppm	Water + 0.2% MeOH	Benzene: from 0.21 (Na-P1) to 1.72 (1.0 DODDMA) Toluene: from 0.84 (Na-X) to 1.98 (1.0 DHDDMA) Ethylbenzene: from 0.81 (Na-P1) to 2.35 (1.0 DODDMA) p-Xylene: from 1.47 (Na-P1) to 1.67 (1.0	1/50	BTEX removal efficiency depends not only on textural parameters and the surfactant used for modification but also on the chemical properties of various organic compounds, such as dipole moment, molar mass, molecular structure, functional groups, time of the sorption process, as well as hydrophobicity of each analyte and other physicochemical and thermochemical properties, and	The results showed that modification of zeolites by surfactants with double-carbon chains improves the sorption properties in the case of benzene, ethylbenzene, and toluene. Simultaneously, it was determined that with an increasing carbon chain length, the sorption efficiency increases. Sorption efficiency depends on the chemical properties of various organic compounds and the duration of the	Wolowicz et al. (2017b)

Table 2 (continued)

Material	Sorption		Fundamental features influencing efficiency		Comments/observations	References
	VOCs	Sorption efficiency [mg/g]	Sorbent/solution ratio	Efficiency		
MOF-AgTz-1	PNP	184.4 at 35 °C and 143.5 at 25 °C	1/2500	active sites to permanently attract benzene molecules. Additionally, microwave crystallization technique requires lower temperatures for synthesis and produces material with a more crystalline structure. The main mechanism that stands behind the sorption process is ion exchange between PNP (p-nitrophenolate anions) and NO ₃ ⁻ anions that are both attached to the surface of the material.	size of MIL-101 nanoparticles differs between 60 and 90 nm. The most sufficient time for effective crystallization of MIL-101 molecular sieve oscillates around 1 h.	Miao et al. (2020)
MOF-199	Phenol and PNP	Phenol = 320, PNP = 357.2	1/4000	The crucial parameter influencing sorption efficiency is pH with optimum ranges between 4.5 and 6. Furthermore, the surface charge is of importance since both sorbates (phenol, PNP) appear in water solution in anionic forms, and hence, positive charge on the surface is required to electrochemically attract desired pollutants.	Adsorption of PNP over MOF-AgTz-1 is a strongly pH-dependent process. Furthermore, pH values are lower after the sorption process compared to the initial pH values of the solution. It might be associated with the deprotonation of the PNP molecules. FTIR analysis revealed the presence of carboxylate functional groups (-COOH) with 1647 cm ⁻¹ band, carbonyl groups (-C=O) with 1354 cm ⁻¹ band, and water molecules with hydroxyl groups (-OH) with a band within a range of 3500–2700 cm ⁻¹ . Above pH 5 of the sorbate solution (phenol, PNP), adsorption efficiency considerably decreased. Furthermore, the surface charge generated by functional groups (-COOH, -C=O, -OH) is of great importance during the removal of phenol and its nitrogenated derivatives. Hydrogen bond and attractive, noncovalent interactions (pi-stacking) are the major mechanisms of sorption.	Giraldo et al. (2017)
MIL-68-Al-RGO	PNP	271 at 30 °C	1/5000	Initial sorbate concentration, ionic strength of the solution, and temperature are the factors that affect the sorption efficiency of MIL-68-Al. It may be concluded that the higher the temperature, the greater the sorption efficiency.		Zhibin et al. (2016)

^a No data available.
^b At temperature of slow pyrolysis process equal to 550 °C.

Fig. 3. The synthesis of mesoporous materials.

in the case of VOCs, FAs must undergo special treatment (e.g. washing and neutralization). The amount of unburned carbon in FAs, their mineralogy, and quality needed in the market offer opportunities for new

research into the modification and exploitation of the unique chemistry of materials synthesized from FAs as future sorption materials for VOCs (Mane et al., 2007).

Fig. 4. The influence of synthesis on mesoporous materials properties.

2.2. Biochars

Biochars are defined in a various way, but in general they are described as “porous, carbonaceous solids produced by the thermochemical conversion of organic materials in an oxygen free atmosphere that have physicochemical properties suitable for safe and long-term storage of carbon in the environment” (Shackley et al., 2012). On the other hand, Lehman and Joseph (2012), stated, that “biochars are a carbon (C)-rich products when biomass such as wood, manure or leaves are heated in a closed container with little or unavailable air”.

VOCs removal from water environments in particular, using biochars, as a bio-based, renewable sorbents, produced at different temperature regimes, using slow pyrolysis (Ahmad et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2019), fast pyrolysis (Spokas et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2017a), but also gasification (Shackley et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2017b) of the whole array of biomass feedstocks including soybean stover, peanut shells (Ahmad et al., 2012), cotton wood (Zhang et al., 2012), sugarcane, neem tree, bamboo tree (Kumar et al., 2019), sugar beet tailings, Brazilian pepper wood (Zhang et al., 2019), pine needles (Ahmad et al., 2013), orange peels (Chen et al., 2011), and rice hulls (Yan et al., 2015), have been assessed thoroughly in recent decade, as a new way to both effectively and economically reduce an excessive amount of VOCs released to surface waters and groundwaters worldwide, via adsorption.

Additionally, as described by Jayawardhana et al. (2018), also organic fraction of municipal solid wastes, could serve as a feedstock to produce biochars via pyrolysis process and simultaneously reduce the amount of landfills areas and valorize such substrates, which seems to be in line with the PDCA approach presented in Fig. 2 for fly-ashes as CCBP. Kumar et al. (2019) have synthesized biochars from sugarcane, neem tree and bamboo tree via slow pyrolysis at three different temperatures (350 °C, 450 °C, and 550 °C) and assessed the capability of these biosorbents to remove six VOCs: benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, from water solutions. Neither chemical nor physical modification of such produced biochar was applied. It was found that the greatest sorption capacity was obtained by neem-based biochar, produced at the highest pyrolysis temperature (550 °C), in respect to toluene molecule. Sorption efficiency equals 65.5 mg/g. Proximate analysis of obtained biochars clearly indicates, that with increasing pyrolysis temperature, carbon (C) content in biochars also increases while hydrogen (H) and oxygen (O) contents decrease. This phenomenon might be associated with the depolymerization of long carbon chains of lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose carbohydrates present in raw biomass feedstocks. While increasing the pyrolysis temperature, the SSA of as received biochars also increases, which is in line with the findings of Yan et al. (2015) and Zhang et al. (2017a).

As observed for SBA-15 and KIT-6 MSMs, VOCs sorption on biochars is favoured when higher pyrolysis temperature is used, because of the better developed SSA and internally linked micropores in the material matrix in which VOCs molecule can freely diffuse and become permanently retained. Reaction kinetics experiments revealed that sorption on such produced biochars is an exothermic and spontaneous process. Additionally, higher C content in all three materials observed once slow pyrolysis at 550 °C was implemented, may be associated with more abundant oxygen-rich functional groups on the surface of biochar, hence greater sorption of hydrophilic VOCs molecules appear (Kumar et al., 2019).

Slow pyrolysis of pine-needles biomass could also serve as a mean to thermochemically synthesize biochars as renewable sorbents for VOCs removal, as presented in the research study performed by Ahmad et al. (2013). Such biochars were synthesized at three different temperatures via slow-pyrolysis: 300 °C, 500 °C and 700 °C. Sorption experiments were carried out in respect to TCE as the prior contaminant present in groundwaters in the vicinity of an industrial complex in Wonju, Gangwon province (South Korea). Biochars have not been

modified, both chemically or physically. Proximate analysis exhibits greater content in C and lower content of H and O of biochars synthesized at higher pyrolytic temperatures, which confirms conclusions drawn from other research studies (Yan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2017a; Kumar et al., 2019). SSA also increases, once higher pyrolytic temperature is used (4.09 m²/g to 390.52 m²/g for biochars synthesized at 300 °C and 700 °C, respectively). Maximum adsorption capacity of TCE was observed for pine-needle based biochar produced at 700 °C, and equals 99.733 mg/g. Different adsorption models (Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, Dubinin-Radushkevish) revealed that the main mechanism of sorption is micropore filling, and that biochars produced in temperatures above 500 °C favours the adsorption of TCE. In addition, TCE adsorption is higher while polarity of the biochar decrease (Karafanil and Dastgheib, 2004). Another interesting approach in synthesizing biochars was shown in the laboratory studies described by Chen et al. (2011). They have used orange peels as a biomass feedstock to produce biochar and have modified it via co-precipitation process with MAG nanoparticles. Subsequent pyrolysis of such mixed materials was performed at three different temperatures: 250 °C, 400 °C, and 700 °C. As obtained, biosorbents were used to remove NAPH and PNT from aqueous media.

Similarity to research outcomes presented by Yan et al. (2015), Ahmad et al. (2013), and Kumar et al. (2019), positive correlation between pyrolysis temperature, SSA, and porosity was observed - the higher the temperature, the higher above mentioned textural parameters of obtained materials. However, modification of raw orange peel biochars with MAG nanoparticles greatly diminish the SSA, independently of the pyrolytic temperature (501 m²/g to 9.4 m²/g at 700 °C, for non-modified and MAG-modified biochars, respectively). Moreover, no increase in both NAPH and PNT adsorption capacity was observed for MAG-modified biochars (e.g. 16.65 mg/g and 17.96 mg/g in respect to NAPH and 294.15 mg/g and 318 mg/g in respect to PNT, for MAG-modified and non-modified orange peel biochars pyrolyzed at 700 °C, respectively). Poorer adsorption capacity of both NAPH and PNT by MAG-modified biochars may be correlated with colmatation of micropores by nano-sized MAG particles and hence no free micropores available for both NAPH and PNT to be adsorbed.

2.3. Zeolites

Regarding the application of synthetic zeolites in the removal of VOCs, many results have been published, which allows a better understanding of the adsorption mechanism and developing techniques that enable the dissemination of zeolites to the market of organic sorbents (Ahmed et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017; Salvestrini et al., 2019). Zeolites such as Na-X, Na-P1, and Na-Y were found to exhibit a marked ability to adsorb BTEX, especially when their surface was modified with organic surfactants (Chao et al., 2012; Xie et al., 2012; Wołowicz et al., 2017a). Surfactant modification drastically alters the chemistry of the zeolites' surface, facilitating the adsorption of nonpolar organic solutes and anions, for which untreated zeolites have a low affinity (Apreutesei et al., 2008). Thus far, many zeolites have been discussed in the literature as potential materials for VOC removal from aqueous solutions; however, this review mainly focuses on synthetic zeolites (Table 1). The environment is degrading and so it is particularly important to look for more sustainable and proecological materials, which could be synthesized from existing wastes. Therefore, the efficiency of zeolites synthesized from FAs was compared with those generated from the reaction of pure reagents.

Temperature is an effective parameter determining the adsorbent capacity, which affects the physical and chemical mechanisms of sorption. Studies available in the literature indicate that with an increase in temperature the efficiency of VOC removal from aqueous solutions decreases (Asl et al., 2020). This could be due to the increase in the internal energy of the adsorbent, which consequently reduces the adsorption capacity. Thermodynamic studies of Asl et al. (2020) ascertained

that the adsorption of BTX onto HZSM-5 was exothermic, feasible, and spontaneous at a lower temperature. These findings were also confirmed by Bandura et al. (2020) in their studies on Na-P1 zeolite modified with chitosan.

Chao et al. (2012), Bandura et al. (2020), and Asl et al. (2020) researched the influence of pH on the effectiveness of sorption and confirmed that the optimal pH for the removal of VOCs from aqueous solutions is 7–8. Generally, a slightly elevated pH favours sorption, in contrast to the low pH values which affect the parameters of organic compounds in solutions and thus slow down the process. Mamaghanifar et al. (2020) also studied the effect of pH on VOC sorption and concluded that pH affects the degree of ionization of various pollutant adsorbents and the separation of various functional groups on active adsorbent sites. Results have demonstrated that BTX removal increases with increasing pH (Simantiraki and Gidarakos, 2015).

Chao et al. (2012) investigated how water solubility and chemical structure influenced the sorption of organic compounds onto modified and unmodified Na-Y zeolites. Because the hydrophilic surface is occupied by water, the organic compounds with low S_w partition only to the organic matter on the zeolite surface to enhance the adsorption capacities. Although the external surface of zeolite is low, the partitioning behavior does not result in occupying the adsorptive sites. The adsorption capacities of the organic compounds with low S_w increase significantly after OTS adsorbs on the zeolite surface. The organically modified zeolite Na-Y shows amphiphilic characteristics with the hydrophobic external surface and the hydrophilic internal pore surface. Organic compounds with relatively higher S_w can adsorb onto the internal porous surface, if their size allows them to enter the pores. Furthermore, Chao et al. (2012) as well as Wołowiec et al. (2017a, 2017b) showed that the value of S_w , molecular size, and functionality are important factors affecting the adsorption capacity of different zeolites, namely Na-Y, Na-X, and Na-P1.

The adsorption capacity of zeolite for VOCs is relatively high due to its pore structure (especially a high mesoporous share) and specific surface that can be easily modified. The Si content of zeolite determines its water resistance, which can be tailored in the synthesis process. Zeolite is regarded as one of the conventional adsorbents for VOCs, thanks to its high adsorption capacity, good thermal stability, and easy reproducibility (Zhu et al., 2020). However, its surface modification can significantly improve the efficiency of VOC removal from aqueous systems. Before modification, zeolite Na-P1 was shown to remove 7% of benzene from the solution, while after modification, the synthetic zeolite removed up to 50% of benzene. In addition, DHDDMA-zeolite Na-P1 was identified as the most effective sorbent (Wołowiec et al., 2017b). It was clearly observed in all experimental studies that the use of a surfactant with a higher carbon chain length for modification increased the sorption efficiency. Modification with surfactants containing two carbon chains further improved the removal of benzene from the solution. This is due to the formation of a more extensive organic layer, in which an organic compound dissolves (Wołowiec et al., 2017b).

The cited research results (Table 1) indicate that synthetic zeolites can be used for removing VOCs in the place of commercially available sorbents (e.g. activated carbon). It was difficult to compare the sorption properties and parameters of various zeolites (Na-Y, Na-X, Na-P1, 4A, ZSM-5) because of the inconsistencies in data presentation (differences in modification methods, sorbent preparation, sorbent/solution ratio, etc.). However, from the literature reviewed, a few zeolites that stand out for their high efficiency of VOC removal were identified. These include OTS-modified zeolite Na-Y, zeolite Na-X synthesized from FAs and modified with HDTMA, and HZSM-5 nanozeolite. Thus, it can be confirmed that surface modification with organic surfactants is more important than the structural and textural parameters of zeolites. From the comparison of materials, it can also be mentioned that the proecological technologies of zeolite synthesis from FAs result in valuable materials as those produced from pure substrates. An objective of further experiments and industrial studies should be to improve the

chemical and physical stability of the modified zeolites, which would allow their use on a larger scale (Muir et al., 2017), taking into account that sorption efficiency depends on factors such as surface modification and chain length of surfactants (Wołowiec et al., 2017b).

2.4. Mesoporous silica

Ordered mesoporous and microporous inorganic solids drew immense attention after they were first synthesized in 1992 by Kresge et al. by the addition of different surfactant molecules to aluminosilicate gels. This is primarily because the pore size of such molecular sieves as well as their surface chemistry can be specifically tailored by the use of a proper organic surfactant (cationic, anionic, nonionic) molecule as a templating agent, which results in the desired materials for specific, individualized purposes. First, the MSM chemically synthesized by Mobil Research and Development Corporation was labeled after the research center as Mobil Composition of Matter (MCM-41). Further alterations made by the use of different surface active molecules (e.g. cationic HDTMA-Br) for the synthesis significantly changed the spatial arrangement of the material rendering lamella-like (MCM-50), cubical (MCM-48), and hexagonal (MCM-41) solids (Narayan et al., 2018). Another type of MSM, named as SBA-15, was synthesized at the University of California Santa Barbara and was named after this research institution (Santa Barbara Amorphous-SBA). To obtain SBA-like MSMs, nonionic surfactants such as PEO, EO, and PAO should be employed and the solution's pH should be maintained below 7 (Zhao et al., 1998). SBA-15 obtained via this route is more stable and has thicker silica walls and larger pore volume as compared to its MCM-41 counterpart, but the hexagonal orientation of pores remains unchanged for both materials (Galarneau et al., 2002). The third member of the MSM family is KIT-6 which is synthesized by using P123 as a templating agent and TEOS as a Si source (Zhou et al., 2018). Contrary to MCM-41 and SBA-15, KIT-6 possesses internally linked, cylindrical pores.

Besides the synthesis of MSMs from pure chemicals, FAs containing large amounts of both silica and alumina can be a good raw material for the formation of geometrically ordered, mesoporous silica molecular sieves. These molecular sieves, which can be obtained from FA by-products, possess a higher pore size and hence are more efficient in the removal of large polar molecules from water solutions and gaseous mixtures. These materials have already been widely used for the adsorption processes, separation, isomerization, and catalysis (Beck et al., 1992; Kresge et al., 1992).

Majchrzak-Kucęba and Nowak (2011) presented a review on the use of 10 types of FAs with different mineralogical and structural compositions, which originated from hard coal and lignite thermal conversion in pulverized coal combustion boilers and circulating fluidized bed boilers. They used the abovementioned FAs as raw materials for the synthesis of MCM-41 molecular sieves. FAs were used as a Si source along with sodium hydroxide (NaOH), HDTMA-Br ($C_{19}H_{42}NBr$), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), and double-distilled water. To obtain an MCM-41 molecular sieve, a fusion synthesis method was applied, as described by Shigemoto et al. (1993), to first extract Si from the FA matrix and then directly synthesize MCM-41 with NaOH in a water solution. XRD patterns showed that effective MCM-41 synthesis was achieved only from 60% FA raw material samples used in the study (six out of 10 samples). Based on this, one could conclude that MCM-41 can be effectively synthesized only when the silica-to-alumina ratio in the FA supernatant after hydrothermal activation with NaOH water solution is greater than or equal to 1.9 (Majchrzak-Kucęba and Nowak, 2011).

Despite the fact that even a small amount of impurities (e.g. Ca, S, or P) can significantly alter the hexagonally ordered, cylindrical channel structure of MCM-41 material, its synthesis using FAs as a raw material with an Si-to-Al ratio of greater than 1.9 is practically feasible. Their use for the removal of certain VOCs (e.g. BTEX) from water solutions would be of advantage since it has not been assessed for this specific purpose so far. Unfortunately, the authors of the discussed publication did not

analyze the textural features of the obtained MCM-41 material, namely the specific surface area, pore size distribution, and percentage share of each pore size. Determination of the above-listed parameters is important to compare the obtained MCM-41 materials to different molecular sieves used for neutralizing numerous volatile contaminants from water and gases. Additionally, these analyses would pave the way to assess, if conversion of fly-ash to MCM-41 is beneficial from the perspective of the dimensions of voids and channels, in which the VOC molecules can diffuse and be permanently retained. Consequently, it would also shed light on whether MCM-41 is more or less predisposed for use as an effective sorbent. Moreover, in the scientific work published by Ghiaci et al. (2004), an MCM-41 material was directly assessed while it was used for the removal of three VOCs - benzene, toluene, and phenol, from contaminated waters. Laboratory experiments were carried out using zeolites modified by HDTMA-Br (organo-clinoptilolite and organo-ZSM-5 with a SiO₂-to-Al₂O₃ ratio of 31 and 88, respectively) and MCM-41 material. The research revealed that MCM-41 is a much better sorbent for all three VOCs, compared to HDTMA-Br-clinoptilolite and two HDTMA-Br-ZSM-5 zeolites. This phenomenon may be explained by the fact that more than twice as much HDTMA-Br was adsorbed onto the surface of the MCM-41 material (913 mmol/kg) compared to 573 mmol/kg in the case of organo-clinoptilolite. Contrary to Ghiaci et al.'s conclusion that it is difficult to synthesize pure MCM-41 molecular sieves, Chang et al. (1999) stated that the FA raw materials treated via fusion method with NaOH water solution and mixed with HDTMA-Br cationic surfactant rendered hexagonally ordered, pure MCM-41 materials. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) of such FA conversion products equaled 735 m²/g, and XRD analysis revealed the abundance of silicon (Si) in the sample because of the strong reflections in the diffractogram of the fused FAs which, most probably, came from the sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃) mineral phase. Based on these researches, the following crucial conclusions can be drawn: first, it is possible to effectively convert FA by-products into MCM-41 materials; second, a fusion method with NaOH water solution ought to be implemented, where the molar Si-to-Al ratio should be greater than or equal to 13.4 in fused FAs; and third, the presence of impurities does not pose any detrimental effect on the MCM-41 structure (Chang et al., 1999; Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020).

Another material from the group of MSMs - SBA-15, was synthesized from FA raw materials by Chandrasekar and Ahn (2008) and Chandrasekar and Won-jin (2008), which were further used for the adsorptive neutralization of carbon dioxide. XRD patterns revealed the poorly ordered mesostructure of the obtained material, probably due to the low Si-to-P123 ratio. XRF analysis, on the other hand, showed that FAs used for the synthesis of SBA-15 were mainly composed of SiO₂ (57.05% wt.) and Al₂O₃ (23.04% wt.) with minor existence of Fe₂O₃ (9.21% wt.), CaO (2.76% wt.), and other oxides such as K₂O, TiO₂, MgO, and P₂O₅. Unfortunately, it is impossible to compare the specific surface area of MCM-41 reported by Majchrzak-Kuceba and Nowak (2011) with that of SBA-15 obtained by Chandrasekar and Ahn (2008) due to the lack of information concerning S_{BET} for the as-synthesized MCM-41. The specific surface area of SBA-15, measured by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method, equaled 407 m²/g. Based on this research, one could conclude that effective neutralization of benzene as one of VOCs could be achieved by using SBA-15, since both carbon dioxide and benzene are of nonpolar nature (Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020).

The third material from the group of MSMs that can be chemically synthesized via FA fusion with sodium hydroxide is KIT-6 (Chandrasekar et al., 2009). Despite the fact that this material was used as an adsorbent of CO₂ from gas streams, its high specific surface area and large cubic symmetry of pores are of huge interest for the prospective removal of VOCs from water mixtures. KIT-6 synthesized using TEOS as a silica source (Zhao et al., 1998; Zhou et al., 2018) possessed a huge specific surface area of 912 m²/g (Baojuan et al., 2010) and a good affinity toward VOCs, such as benzene and cyclohexane. However, KIT-6 and its phenyl-grafted,

functionalized derivative developed by Baojuan et al. (2010) have not been employed for VOC removal from water solutions. Nevertheless, the assessment of its removal efficiency compared to the other mesoporous silicas revealed that KIT-6 and phenyl-grafted-KIT-6 were the most effective, probably due to the homogenous surface coverage by PTES and the larger pores, where complex PTES molecules can more easily penetrate and freely diffuse.

2.5. MOFs

Multiple variations in the textural parameters of sorbents and their chemical composition trigger the need to develop and synthesize novel materials with tailored pore diameter and surface chemistry to increase their adsorption capacity toward specific, undesired contaminants in water solutions including VOCs. In recent years, there has been increasing interest in novel, hybrid, ultraporos materials such as MOFs and their potential applicability as effective and easy-to-regenerate sorbents (Silva et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2019a). Their enormous potential has also been evaluated in terms of: heterogeneous catalysis (Foster and Cheetham, 2003); capture and storage of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and hydrogen (H₂) (Yingwei and Yang, 2007; Germain et al., 2009; Thomas, 2007); gas separation (Long et al., 2006); and drug delivery (Gutowska et al., 2005; Hermes et al., 2005). This is mostly because MOFs are easily obtained at room temperatures and by applying the whole array of divalent, trivalent, or even tetravalent cations as inorganic templates for achieving tunable, three-dimensional structure, and well-developed porosity and pore size (Ferey, 2008).

Despite the fact that there is huge interest in the use of MOFs for the removal of dyes from water environments (Haque et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2012) and various gases, such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂), ammonia (NH₃), chlorine (Cl₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and dichloromethane (CH₂Cl₂) (Britt et al., 2008), their applicability as a medium to remove or neutralize VOCs from water solutions has not been extensively assessed.

Jhung et al. (2006), in particular, have synthesized an MIL-101 nanoporous material and tested its applicability in the sorption of benzene (C₆H₆) from water solutions. Synthesis was carried out via the microwave irradiation method at 210 °C for 1 h using an EtOH solution of 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid and chromium (III) nitrate nonahydrate (Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O). N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm measurements revealed the largest specific surface area of all the materials assessed in this review, which reached a value of 3900 m²/g. The XRD analysis revealed broad reflections indicating the presence of small MIL-101 particles. XRF analysis and FTIR measurements were not carried out. TGA revealed the stability of the material up to 275 °C.

It was experimentally proved that MIL-101 can remove 16.7 mmol/g of benzene at an initial concentration of 1000 ppm. Sorption mechanisms were not specified; nevertheless, it may be concluded that the large pore diameters of MIL-101 favour the diffusion of benzene molecule within its framework. Additionally, the small particle sizes (nanograins) of MIL-101 render more active sites to effectively attract electronegative, nonpolar benzene molecules. Giraldo et al. (2017), on the other hand, synthesized MOF-199 from pure chemical reagents using the solvothermal method (Nguyen et al., 2012) by mixing an EtOH water solution with DMF and solid salts such as organic 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid and inorganic copper nitrate trihydrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O) (Rowell and Yaghi, 2005; Tranchemontagne et al., 2008). The obtained MOF-199 was employed for the removal of aqueous phenol and its nitrogenated derivative - PNP. The specific surface area, measured by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method, of the obtained material equaled 2271 m²/g. Based on the cryogenic nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm measurements and the shape of the material, MOF-199 was delineated as containing mostly homogenous micropores, and so their size is less than 2 nm, according to the IUPAC classification. XRD and XRF analyses and TGA measurements were not

performed. However, having performed all, three, above-listed analyses, it would be easier to deduce the structural features of the material (XRD), its precise chemical composition (XRF) and thermal effects, associated with the structural changes of the material in the function of temperature and mass loss (TGA). TGA analyses in particular, might answer the question if the material's structure is thermally stable within the temperature range of sewage sludge, where excessive VOCs concentration is still a problematic issue.

Mid-IR spectroscopy revealed broad bands in the range of 2700–3500 cm^{-1} which indicated the presence of water molecules and hydroxyl groups (-OH) in the structure of MOF-199. The presence of carboxylic functional groups (-COOH) was identified based on strong, stretching vibrations at 1647 cm^{-1} . In addition, a strong peak at 1354 cm^{-1} was found which was associated with the stretching vibrations of carbonyl groups (-C=O). It is worth highlighting that copper used in the synthesis of desired MOF-199 material was detected in the IR spectra by a band at 505 cm^{-1} which was associated with Cu—O stretching vibrations (Lin et al., 2012).

Both sorption of phenol and PNP on MOF-199 is a strongly pH-dependent process, which showed the highest efficiency at a pH less than or equal to 4.3. This phenomenon may be explained by the surface charge of MOF-199. With a decrease in pH, its surface charge becomes positive, and hence via electrostatic interactions, phenolate anions might be effectively attracted and retained.

Zhibin et al. (2016) changed the structure of MIL-68 MOF with the use of RGO and used this sorbent for the removal of PNP. Solvothermal method was used for the synthesis. The specific surface area measured by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method at 77 K of the MIL-68-Al-ROD equaled 761.97 m^2/g . Additionally, the material was mostly composed of micro- and mesopores, according to Barrett-Joyner-Halenda measurements, with a medium pore size of around 9 nm, according to the IUPAC classification. X-ray diffractograms of the material exhibited large reflections complementary with those reported by Han et al. (2015) for similar MOF-RGO. Reflections that came probably from graphene oxide particles were also noted, which may be related to the insufficient reduction of graphene oxide.

Mid-IR analysis showed the presence of hydroxyl groups (-OH) via 3425 cm^{-1} band, carbonyl groups (C=O) via 1512 and 1701 cm^{-1} bands, and C=C covalent bonds via 1411 and 1587 cm^{-1} bands. Furthermore, a characteristic peak was noted at 754 cm^{-1} and C-O-C peak at 991 cm^{-1} . Benzene ring-related C—H vibrations were visible at 1097 cm^{-1} . SEM microimaging revealed the formation of nanosized crystallites probably due to the formation of coordination bonds between Al^{3+} cations and numerous carboxyl (-COOH) and hydroxyl (-OH) functional groups on the RGO's surface.

MIL-68-Al-RGO material exhibited the greatest sorption efficiency toward PNP when 15% loading of RGO was introduced into MIL-68-Al (307.38 mg/g of the material). This might be associated with the largest surface area of all materials assessed in the described study. Experiments also proved that the sorption of nitrogenated phenolic compounds is a temperature-dependent process—the greater the temperature, the higher the sorption efficiency. Similar to the outcomes of the experimental research performed by Giraldo et al. (2017), the greatest sorption efficiency of MIL-68-Al-RGO was achieved at a pH less than or equal to 5. This may be explained by the form in which PNP molecule appears in the water solution at this pH and the hydrophobic interactions occurring between the surface of the sorbent and sorbate. However, further reduction of the solution's pH leads to the deterioration of the MIL-68-Al-RGO structure, and hence drastically decreases the sorption efficiency.

An advantage is that desorption experiments were carried out using MeOH and EtOH to determine the strength by which PNP is attracted by MIL-68-Al-RGO. After five cycles of sorption/desorption, it was concluded that MeOH is more effective compared to EtOH and sorption of PNP after sorbent regeneration equaled 271.82 mg/g . This might indicate that regeneration can be achieved without severe loss in sorption

efficiency by the use of MeOH as a desorbing media. Furthermore, mid-IR measurements were performed to identify the type of chemical interactions and hence the mechanism of sorption between PNP and MIL-68-Al-RGO. The IR-spectra of pure sorbent and that of PNP after sorption showed a slight shift in C—O—C vibrations to 1000 cm^{-1} from 991 cm^{-1} . This may be straightforward evidence of the formation of hydrogen bonds between PNP and MIL-68-Al-RGO. Moreover, the RGO electron-rich regions can attract the nonpolar benzene ring of PNP molecules, thus making the sorption process independent of the isomeric form of nitrogenated phenol compound. Therefore, it would be possible to remove such compounds from multicomponent water systems.

2.6. Summary

The impact of modifications by different surfactants on textural parameters and porosity are displayed in the previous publication (Muir and Bajda, 2016). The analysis of textural parameters revealed that the modification reduced by up to 70% of S_{BET} and up to 35% of V_{tot} 0.99. The hydrophilic head of surfactant is usually too large to penetrate mesoporous materials pores - the process occurred only on the outer surface of the sorbent. The external surface was responsible for the majority of the sorption. The surface area reduction was more intense for zeolite synthesized from fly ash than the pure reagents and it was caused by the smaller pores' shares. Many researchers proved that when the texture parameters decrease, the sorption increases. With an increasing amount of the surfactant attached to the zeolite's surface during the modification procedure, sorption efficiency increases. In the case of BTEX sorption on organo-materials, hydrocarbons dissolved in the organic layer of surfactant.

3. The influence of features on sorption efficiency

3.1. Fly ash

FAs were investigated as a potential surrogate for the sorption of various VOC pollutants from wastewater (Banerjee et al., 1997; Sharan et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2013). All the presented batch experiments demonstrated that coal FAs can potentially remove hydrophobic, organic petroleum contaminants including o-xylene, phenol, and BTEX (Table 2). FAs are characterized by a varied specific surface area of 5–10 m^2/g (Table 1) and a poorly developed pore structure in comparison with the products obtained from it, such as synthetic zeolites (Cheerarot and Jaturapitakkul, 2004). It was observed that the sorption effect is related to the greater percentage of carbon content inherent to the ash (Banerjee et al., 1997). Sorption capacity toward VOCs increases with the increase in the carbon content of coal FA (Zhu et al., 2020). However, during the experiments, the relationship between percent carbon and percent sorption was not found to be linear (Banerjee et al., 1997). The nonlinear effect may be attributed to the variation in carbon quality as a raw coal product combined with variable combustion procedures. In addition, the complex mineral properties of coal may interfere with the sorptive properties of carbon in the coal FA by-products (Gisi et al., 2016). In general, coal FAs offer less of this nonpolar, natural, solid organic substrate because it inherently contains less amount of carbon, less surface area of carbon material, and less mineral components inherent to coal as compared to other mesoporous materials described in this review (Miricioiu and Niculescu, 2020). Moreover, as described in a previous chapter, the utilization of FAs in water involves the potential leaching process, which will lead to secondary environmental pollution. This could limit the wider use and industrial applications of FAs. Therefore, it is important to utilize the great potential of FAs as a substrate for the synthesis of functionalized mesoporous materials.

3.2. Biochars

Reviewed studies related to the thermochemical synthesis of biochars as renewable sorbents, mostly via slow-pyrolysis process, clearly demonstrate their relatively high potential for the neutralization of certain VOCs molecules from water environments. The greatest influence on adsorption capacities toward NAPH, PNT (Chen et al., 2011), TCE (Ahmad et al., 2013), benzene, toluene, methyl chloride, xylene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride (Kumar et al., 2019) present in waters seem to be applied pyrolytic temperature and type of used feedstock as raw material. Furthermore, microporosity of the material, not its mesoporous share, was described as a decisive parameter to be taken into consideration once planning to implement biochars for the removal of VOCs from water solutions (Ahmad et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2019). This biochar's feature greatly differs from this observed for fly-ashes, synthetic zeolites, MSMs, and MOFs, where mesoporosity, not microporosity determines capability to adsorb VOCs by these molecular sieves. In most reviewed studies, pore filling, neither the ion exchange nor physical adsorption was the main mechanism responsible for VOCs removal.

3.3. Zeolites

Studies in the literature clearly demonstrate how the concentration of some VOCs may be reduced when synthetic zeolites are used as sorbents (Muir et al., 2017). Based on their results, natural zeolites may be considered as effective sorbents for the removal of organic compounds from natural water (Table 2). Sorption of VOCs on zeolites is mainly influenced by reaction time and pH and ionic strength of the solution (Veerapandian et al., 2019). Experiments carried out on aqueous samples simulating natural water systems have revealed that different VOCs and their mixtures can be simultaneously removed by applying different types of zeolites (Wołowiec et al., 2017a). Sorption capacity of zeolites was found to depend on their textural parameters and the physicochemical properties of the petroleum products such as density (Bandura et al., 2017). One of the significant features influencing the sorption of VOCs is the surface area (Table 1). It was noted that materials with a higher S_{BET} can act as more effective sorbents, and the sorption efficiency was estimated at 6.5, 18.0, and 23 mg/g for Na-X (S_{BET} 282 m²/g), ZSM-5 (S_{BET} 398 m²/g), and Na-Y (S_{BET} 470 m²/g), respectively. The sorption process involved the filling of mesopores and covering of external surface. In many cases, the greater the proportion of mesopores, the better was the sorption parameters (Asl et al., 2020; Bandura et al., 2020). It is concluded that adsorption capacities are well related to surface hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity and structural features, such as micropore volume and pore size of high-silica materials (Jiang et al., 2018). The experimental results clearly show that surface modification improves the sorption properties of zeolites (Megías-Sayago et al., 2020). Despite the negative effect on the textural parameters, and especially the reduction of specific surface area, a significant improvement in the efficiency of VOC removal from aqueous solutions has been observed (Chao et al., 2012; Franus et al., 2014; Szala et al., 2015; Wołowiec et al., 2017a). This is due to the dissolution of volatile compounds in the organic layer of the surfactant used on the surface of the minerals. By using high-silica zeolites, the undesired competitive adsorption of background organic matter in natural water could potentially be prevented.

3.4. Mesoporous silica

Based on the main conclusions from the literature studies, concerning the affinity and behavior of MSMs during the removal of undesired organic molecules from water solutions, the main aspect that should be considered once the material to be used is decided is the size of pores and their distribution within the material and surface

charge of the molecular sieve (Kresge et al., 1992; Tian et al., 2009). In addition, the spatial orientation of the voids and cavities within the material seems to be another key factor to be considered as it affects the sorption capability of certain MSMs. For instance, despite the fact that KIT-6, described by Baojuan et al. (2010), possesses three-dimensional, cubical, and interwoven pores, and exhibits a slightly lower specific surface area compared to MCM-41 (912 and 1088 m²/g, respectively), it is a better sorbent of VOCs as it allows more uniform surface coverage by PTES molecules and hence has a more homogenous surface charge that can more effectively and permanently attract polar, electronegative molecules of certain VOCs. Still, a need for experimental and laboratory studies is desired, in order to assess if the simultaneous sorption of two or more chemicals belonging to the VOC family from water solutions is a pH- or concentration-dependent process and if the coexistence of few VOCs in solution enhances or diminishes the neutralization of specific volatile organic compounds. Furthermore, such experiments would better mimic and reflect the real, natural conditions occurring in surface water reservoirs and rivers.

3.5. MOFs

MOFs should also be seriously considered as a very prospective and adjustable sorbents (Zhu et al., 2019b; Miao et al., 2020). Due to the possibility to interchangeably introduce nodal cations of different electric charges to the material matrix and change the size of ionic radius, the chance of specifically adjusting the pore size of MOF to obtain a desired organic molecule might be very interesting to verify experimentally. Additionally, one should take into account the chemical nature of the organic ligand applied as a building unit to the framework of the molecular sieve, as it could significantly enhance the sorption properties of the material (Ferey, 2008; Nazmul et al., 2013). To summarize, the initial concentration of specific VOC contaminants, sorbent/sorbate ratio, specific surface area and pore size of the sorbent as well as percentage share of each pore size, and simultaneous cosorption of multiple VOCs are some aspects that should be researched and experimentally verified from both cognitive and industrial application perspective.

3.6. Summary

The efficiency of sorption depends on the chemical properties of the various organic compounds (dipole moment, molar mass, molecule structure, and the time of the sorption process as well as hydrophobicity of each analytes) and zeolites properties; like the Si/Al ratio, texture parameters, particle size, and external cation exchange capacity (Fig. 5). The mechanism of the sorption consists of dissolving the VOCs into the organic layer of the surfactant more on the penetration of the organic solution into the mesopores. More detailed information is presented in publication Wołowiec et al. (2017a).

From the articles cited, it can be concluded that adsorption capacity in terms of VOC is an increasing function of the mesopore volume. Further analysis of sorption kinetics, mostly using the Langmuir and the Dubinin-Radushkevich equations, shows increases of both the equilibrium constant and the adsorption energy with the mesopore volume, indicating that mesopores facilitate the adsorption of the adsorbates in the inner and narrow micropores, which contain adsorptive sites with higher adsorption energies (Hsieh et al., 2010). The results of the presented research studies have demonstrated the importance of mesopores in enhancing the adsorption capacity of synthetic mesoporous materials in aqueous solutions, especially for the adsorption of larger organic molecules (Hsieh et al., 2010).

4. Perspective materials

As stated previously, still MSMs such as MCM-41, MCM-48, SBA-15, and KIT-6 have not been extensively assessed for the neutralization of VOCs in wastewaters. These materials could be synthesized from

Fig. 5. Comparison of the sorbents derived from fly-ash and those synthesized from pure chemical reagents.

cheap and easily accessible raw materials including FAs; therefore, this trend would comply with the valorization of wastes and their recirculation to chemical synthesis as substrates, which directly complies with the concept of circular economy and zero waste (Hartmann and Bischof, 1999). Furthermore, the functionalization of these materials by organic or inorganic surfactants, such as HDTMA-Br, would be preferable to positively charge their surface and enhance their affinity to negatively charged or nonpolar molecules such as toluene or xylene isomers, which, besides other toxic chemicals, belong to the group of VOCs.

Furthermore, mostly due to the possibility of tailoring the pore structure and size of pores along with the use of double-charged, triple-charged, or even quadruple-charged cations, MOFs are very promising alternatives to zeolites or activated carbons which are already employed for wastewater purification. Their synthesis could be performed at temperatures below 100 °C (Lee et al., 2013), and the methods used for mixing the inorganic template with organic linkers allow countless variations in their manufacture of these materials in terms of structure, texture, and chemical properties (Ferey, 2008).

ZIF, a new hybrid class of MOF comprising imidazole linkers that mimic the spatial structure of aluminosilicate zeolites, could also be employed for the sorption of VOCs from waters (Yang and Chung, 2013). In recent years, they have been applied as gas separators (Bux et al., 2011), heterogenous catalysts (Surrender and Carreon, 2010; Wang et al., 2013; Wee et al., 2013), and drug delivery mediums (Sun et al., 2013). Therefore, their synthesis and application as sorbents for the removal of toxic contaminants from waters would be advantageous and desirable from the perspective of experimental verification of their efficiency, chemical stability, selectivity, and reusability.

Finally, hydrothermal treatment of FAs leads to the formation of synthetic zeolites with an improved specific surface area. Going a step further, it is possible to increase the mechanical strength of FAs by gluing the carbon fibers together into a synthetic material. The resulting samples (zeolite/C composite), which were studied by Okada et al. (2005), showed enhanced adsorption for polar molecules such as ammonia (NH₃), water vapor (H₂O), and MeOH. The increase of micropore volume in such a composite material is beneficial to improving the adsorption capacity. In addition, the

polar functional groups of zeolite/C composites may enhance the adsorption of VOCs. More importantly, both the development of micropore structure and surface modification contributed to enhancing the adsorption selectivity (Xue et al., 2019). ZSM-5/MCM-41 composite was tested by Li et al. (2019) for the sorption of vapor VOCs. Their results presented new insights with a great research potential for the removal of low concentration of VOCs at the industrial scale. Considering some of the first attempts made to use composites for the removal of organic pollutions, it can be concluded that these materials have high application potential.

5. Conclusion

Several authors have analyzed the adsorption of VOCs from gaseous streams using various FAs, synthetic and natural zeolites, MSMs (MCM-41, MCM-48, SBA-15, KIT-6), MOFs (MIL-101), biochar and ZIFs (ZIF-8, ZIF-9). However, only a few of them confirmed their applicability in the neutralization of toxic compounds from water systems and sewage sludge. Synthetic zeolites (Na-Y, Na-X, 4A, Na-P1, HZSM-5, ZSM-5) were found to be effective alternatives to the currently used steam stripping or air stripping in combination with carbon adsorption off-gas treatment. However, the most impressive results for VOC removal were reported for MSMs and MOFs. These materials can absorb 100 times more organic compounds than FAs or zeolites. This confirms that the fundamental features influencing the sorption efficiency are surface area, surface charge, and the share of micro- and mesopores. Moreover, the possibility of surface modification with organic salts, in which the VOCs later dissolve, is critical (Boycheva et al., 2019).

Future research objectives, which would bring new insights concerning the use of novel, functionalized materials as sorbents for toxic water-insoluble compounds, should emphasize their tailoring toward specific compounds, effective surface modification to enhance simultaneous cosorption of cationic and anionic chemicals, and the ability to be fully regenerated after sorption and reused for the same sorption process without the loss of sorption capability, efficiency, and selectivity. Moreover, these novel, functionalized materials could be easily manufactured from industrial wastes such as FAs. This approach

is economically and ecologically beneficial, as it can close the life cycle of hazardous FA wastes.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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